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Raising Gender Equality for Ethnic Minority Women in the Mountains of Northwest Vietnam

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Astract:

This article uses interviews with married women to understand the situation of gender equality in family labor in ethnic minorities in the northwest mountains of Vietnam. In addition, the study used in-depth interviews with government officials who are implementing policies to improve gender equality in these localities to explore outstanding contradictions in improving inequality for ethnic minority women. The content of the survey revolves around the division of labor, access to resources, decision-making ability in 3 areas of family labor: production activities, reproduction activities and community activities. The results of the study show that although the position between men and women is balanced, men still hold more power in the family and women are said to do light, odd jobs but in fact are much more strenuous. Women's access to resources is also more limited than men's, many of whom do not have the right to make important family decisions. Contradictions in the implementation of gender equality are also explored. Since then, the study proposes solutions to improve equality for ethnic minority women in the Northwest mountains in particular and Vietnam in general

Keywords: Gender equality, women, ethnic minorities.

1. Introduction

Over the past several decades, gender equality has emerged as a central theme in global human rights and development forums (Tolo Østebø, 2015). The number of advocates for gender equality is steadily increasing and is no longer limited to feminist-inspired activists. National governments, donors, civil society organizations, and transnational organizations such as the World Bank have all developed gender policies that demonstrate their commitment to the global women's rights movement. Today, gender equality is an international issue, a concern for all of humanity, and one of the eight millennium development goals (Thomas, 2007).

In Vietnam, the cause of women's liberation has been of interest to the Party and the State since the beginning of the revolution. The slogan "equal rights of men and women" was affirmed from the first Constitution of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam (1946). The correct views and policies of the Party and the State, along with the achievements of 30 years of renovation, the material and spiritual life of Vietnamese families have been significantly improved, with profound changes in the structure, structure and relationships of family members.

Women increasingly have the opportunity to participate and affirm their great role in socio-economic activities, especially in the field of material production. In addition, there is a trend of more and more men taking on jobs that were previously considered women's. With the changing functioning of individuals in the family, the gap of gender inequality in family labor is gradually narrowing. Gender equality in family labor has become an inevitable trend, a measure of the progress and happiness of each family. However, although the law stipulates that in the family, husband and wife are equal in all aspects, discussing and deciding on all common issues, sharing all jobs as well as taking care of children and parents, in fact, the working time of women in the family is often longer than that of men. In the family men are still considered the breadwinners, have the right to decide big issues and be representatives outside the community, while domestic work, taking care of family members is still considered a "vocation" of women, considered a chore, nameless, has no value. Especially in remote and ethnic minority areas, gender inequality in family labor is still going strong, and the position of women in the family is still low.

The Northwest is an area with an important strategic location in terms of socio-economy, defense - security and foreign affairs of our country, where more than 20 ethnic minorities reside, with a diversity of historical origins and social and cultural characteristics. In order to develop the Northwest region, the development of human resources of ethnic minorities is one of the important and urgent tasks. The article presents an overview of the area and ethnic groups, analyzes psychological characteristics, personalities of ethnic minorities, ethnic stereotypes associated with the necessary characteristics of quality human resources. Due to the low level of economic, social and cultural development, gender inequality among ethnic minority families in the Northwest is quite widespread and heavier than in many other regions in the country. The conservative nature of the traditional division of labor by gender, is still evident in ethnic minority families. Because of low production and income conditions, women participate in most production work. Moreover, the use of social services, the means to help reduce the burden of domestic work of ethnic minority families is still very small, not enough to free women from the hard worries of family life today. Therefore, ethnic minority women in the Northwest often have to work with great intensity, long working hours, seemingly absent rest conditions, few opportunities to access resources to develop, improve their own capacity, their ability to make decisions and enjoy benefits is generally much lower than men.

Gender equality in domestic labor is not a new research topic, but has always been topical, always receiving the attention of scientists not only domestically but also internationally and increasingly interested in many different aspects and angles. However, there is currently no work to fully study gender equality in ethnic minority family workers. Therefore, this study uses qualitative research methods to find out the conflicts about gender equality in family labor and the aspirations of ethnic minority women in the Northwest.

2. Theoretical basis

2.1. Conception of gender equality and labor in the family

2.1.1. Concept of gender equality

According to the provisions of Article 5 of the Law on Gender Equality (2007), gender equality is an environment in which men and women hold equal positions and roles and enjoy the same educational, economic and social benefits. This implies that men and women have access to, use the same resources for personal gain and national development (1979 United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women). Accordingly, there should be reasonable treatment between men and women based on the recognition of gender differences in order to ensure equality in terms of participation and benefit. At the same time, attaching interests is personal responsibility to society and the community. Most importantly, gender equality means that men and women enjoy the fruits equally according to the 2013 Constitution, article

26 that "men and women are equal in all aspects". According to the requirements of today's society, gender equality needs to be linked to the perspective of development, economic growth and social justice. Old notions of discrimination need to be eradicated and rejected in all its forms.

2.1.2. Conception of labor in the family

Labor is an economic category. Labor is defined as the process of influencing the human subject on nature thereby creating products suitable to his own needs. This implies that labor is a human being who exerts physical strength and intellect through the use of tools of labor to influence nature for a certain purpose. This process is inevitable for every metabolism between man and nature. Thus, labor is the source of all material wealth (C. Marx and Ph.D., 1995).

The family is the cell of society. Domestic workers play an important role in the survival and development of society. Family labor is understood as an activity aimed at performing the functions of family members, ensuring the survival and development of family cells in particular and society in general (Nguyen Le Thu, 2017). Moving activities and families in general are diverse and rich. However, under any conditions, a family needs to meet at a minimum the physical and spiritual needs of its members. Dr. Eatgghen points out that domestic labor is divided into two main activities, including labor that produces material wealth and labor that reproduces labor. Besides, work in the family can also be divided into factors such as household business production, housework and member care and social interaction (Nguyen Huu Minh, 2008). The views of Tran Van Anh and Le Ngoc Hung (2000) divide family labor on the basis of the nature of the product created. Accordingly, this includes the activity of creating commodity products or income and activities that do not directly generate goods or income. Synthesizing the above perspectives, this study approaches domestic labor through three factors: production activities, reproduction activities, and community activities.

Production: is the whole human activity aimed at creating material products or products and services that satisfy different purposes. Production labor activities are associated with the process of formation and development of human society. Since ancient times, people have used labor tools to create products that serve the needs of human life. As society gradually becomes modern, exchange and sale develop, production activities are understood as activities that are paid or generate income related to production, purchase, employment, etc. At the same time, csc this production activity is permitted in accordance with national laws.

Reproduction activity: is an activity aimed at caring for and maintaining the family. Specifically, activities such as cooking, washing clothes, cleaning the house, taking care of children and the elderly. Reproduction plays an essential role in maintaining life in particular and the survival of society in general. These activities are mainly borne by women and are considered unpaid labor. At the same time, this activity is difficult to convert into economic value. **Community activities:** understood as jobs related to communication, demonstrating the relationship of the family with the community and society. Related activities such as hospitality, festivals, community activities.

2.2. Conception of gender equality in family labor

2.2.1. Concept of gender equality in family labor

Gender equality in family labor is the fact that men and women in the family have the same positions, roles and opportunities (Nguyen Le Thu, 2012). This is understood to mean that they have equal opportunities and conditions in accessing and participating in domestic labor. There is no kind of knowledge or profession that is exclusive to men. Chi has jobs that suit the abilities and interests of the individuals. Gender equality in family labor is the basis for each individual to maximize their potential capacity to maintain the survival and development of the family in particular and society in general. At the same time, they have the right to enjoy

commensurate with the level of contribution to the family and society. This implies that the old ideas and ideas ingrained in the idea of respecting men and women need to be eliminated and eliminated.

2.2.2. Measuring gender equality at work

According to the study Nguyen Le Thu (2017), the tools for assessing gender equality in family labor are shown as follows: First, the division of family labor from a gender perspective. The division of labor by gender is understood as men and women performing different tasks and responsibilities in the family. According to structural-functional theory, the division of labor is governed by biological and social factors. The gender division of labor is associated with social notions of status, social inequality, and subconsciously ingrained notions of the role of men and women. Therefore, this is a way of assessing the status of gender equality in the human community.

Second, access to resources. According to the concept of gender equality (Nguyen Le Thu, 2012), men and women have equal opportunities to access different resources. Resources can be land, jobs, technology, capital, education... Currently, there are different levels of access to resources on the basis of gender. Therefore, access to resources is a measure of the disparity in resource allocation from a gender perspective. Third, family decision-making. The Law on Gender Equality (2007) stipulates that spouses are equal in discussing and making decisions related to the family. Nevertheless. Thus, gender inequality arises when all or most of the decisions in the family are determined by only one gender.

2.2.3. Manifestations of gender inequality in family workers

In the study of Nguyen Le Thu (2017), gender equality in family labor is based on the division of family labor in three aspects: production activities, reproduction activities and community activities.

About production activities

- + Division of labor between spouses in production: employment, trade ...
- + Access to production resources such as loans, land
- + The right to make decisions in choosing, changing the direction of production and use of capital

On reproduction activities:

- + Division of labor between spouses in activities such as cooking, taking care of children and the elderly, washing clothes, cleaning and repairing utensils
- + Access to resources such as family money management, family planning measures
- + The right to make decisions in the use of contraception, having children and family expenses

About community activities

- + Division of labor in community activities
- + Right to access community activities
- + The right to make decisions to participate in community activities

3. Research Methodology

Qualitative research: conducted through the method of in-depth interviews. There were two subjects participating in this study, one was an ethnic minority woman living with her husband, the other was a village

and commune official who implemented policies to improve gender equality today. The survey area is ethnic minority communities in 4 northwestern mountainous provinces: Dien Bien, Hoa Binh, Lai Chau and Son La.

The study conducted 37 group interviews for ethnic minority women in households (345 participants in total) and 15 in-depth interviews with government officials (15). Group interviews aim to capture the local context of gender equality in domestic workers in ethnic minorities and help the study to get a picture of social realities as well as the aspirations of women in domestic labor. Meanwhile, in-depth interviews use a semi-structured approach to approach individual state officials to delve into the contradictions that exist in labor inequality here.

The content of the interviews focused on the following issues: (1) The current state of the division of labor in activities: production, reproduction, community; (2) People's conceptions of how the division of labor in the family are justified, (3) What contradictions remain in the process of promoting gender equality.

Our study was conducted in the mountainous regions of the Northwest with a total of 345 married ethnic minority women between 2018 and 2020. In terms of age, the majority are aged 25-35, accounting for 54.3%, followed by the 35-40 age range, accounting for 18.7%. In terms of education level, the proportion of women with secondary education is the highest, accounting for 37.5%, followed by primary education with 31.3%. In particular, the illiterate of mothers is not small, accounting for 14.7%. In terms of employment, most households in the northwest mountainous ethnic minority areas work in agricultural production (farming, animal husbandry) (34.7%) and craft jobs such as weaving and knitting (31.8%). Many households combine both flax cultivation and weaving. The number of service traders accounts for a decent proportion with 15.6%, only a few have to work for hire (5.1%) with heavy work such as loading and unloading.

Table 1. Demographics of group interview participants

Characteristic		Amount	Proportion
<i>People</i>	<i>Thai</i>	66	19,0%
	<i>Muong</i>	74	21,5%
	<i>Buttock</i>	48	14,0%
	<i>Knife</i>	62	18,0%
	<i>Different</i>	95	27,5%
Sum		345	100,0%
<i>Age range</i>	< 25	59	17,0%
	[25; 30)	96	27,7%
	[30; 35)	92	26,6%
	[35; 40)	65	18,7%
	> 40	35	10,0%
Sum		345	100,0%
<i>Education</i>	<i>High school</i>	57	16,5%
	<i>Middle school</i>	129	37,5%
	<i>Primary education</i>	108	31,3%
	<i>Illiteracy</i>	51	14,7%
Sum		345	100,0%
<i>Affair</i>	<i>Agricultural production</i>	120	34,7%
	<i>Weaving, knitting</i>	110	31,80%
	<i>Trade in services</i>	54	15,6%
	<i>Employed (loading and unloading, sub-construction)</i>	18	5,1%
	<i>Different</i>	44	12,8%
Sum		345	100,0%

Source: survey research

4. Research results

4.1. Gender equality in production activities

4.1.1. Division of labor

In agriculture, the study surveyed 8 types of work in Table 2, there were 4 activities in which the participation rate of both spouses was the highest, namely: Sowing and transplanting: 48.7%; harvest 42%; product preservation 59.7%; care for livestock and poultry: 51%, even many production jobs that used to be considered "private jobs" of women such as sowing, transplanting, and caring for livestock and poultry, now the proportion of both spouses participating is also the highest. This shows the trend of cooperation and equality in agricultural activities between spouses in ethnic minority families in the Northwest.

Table 2. The role of women in agricultural production

Performer Type of work	Wife	Husband	Both	Different
	%	%	%	%
Civet harrow	4,9%	60,8%	27,5%	6,8%
Sowing, transplanting	31,2%	14,6%	48,7%	5,5%
Care, gardening	51,9%	17,3%	24,0%	6,8%
Deep spraying	12,5%	64,7%	15,0%	7,8%
Harvest	37,5%	14,0%	42,0%	6,5%
Product preservation	24,5%	6,8%	59,7%	9,0%
Making a barn for cattle	3,9%	61,8%	24,0%	10,3%
Take care of livestock and poultry	31,5%	11,8%	51,0%	5,7%

Source: archaeological research

Weaving is a popular craft among all ethnic minorities in the Northwest Mountains. "Weaving and embroidery are considered the work of women, daughters from 10-12 years old have been instructed, guided and acquainted with the jobs related to weaving" (Tay women grow cotton weaving fabric). Moreover, mastery in weaving is considered a "criterion, a girl's virtue". The survey results showed that the weaving industry had 65.8% of women participating. Income from textile activities has contributed largely to the finances of these households. In the past few years, traditional weaving has become a way out of poverty for ethnic people.

"In addition to making products to serve the needs of families and compatriots in the region, we also take orders from foreign tourists." (Muong woman, 28 years old dien Bien province).

"Income from weaving and embroidery makes up an important part of my family's economy, becoming the main source of income, making family activities more comfortable." (Hmong woman, 34 years old, Lao Cai province).

Table 3. The role of women in textile, service trade, and employment activities

Performer Type of work	Wife	Husband	Both	Different
	%	%	%	%
Trade and services	51,6%	31,7%	15,9%	0,8%
Weaving, knitting	65,8%	5,7%	13,4%	15,1%
Employed (loading and unloading, sub-construction)	18,7%	37,6%	24,7%	19,0%

Source: archaeological research

In recent years in the northwest mountainous region, due to the development of tourism, a part of ethnic minority families have switched to new professions such as: tour guides, doing tourism services at home - the

form of picking up overnight or long-term stays in the family and collecting money for services such as meals, sleep, take a medicinal bath.

"The income from serving tourists can bring us about 41 USD / month, this is not a small source of income for us." - (Tay women in Hoa Binh).

"We often travel away from town to rent lodgings and sell souvenirs to foreign tourists." (group of women from Sapa, Lao Cai).

And especially, the people who make most of the products for tourists, from brocade products to other items such as bamboo knitting are women. It can be seen that with this work, women are making an increasing contribution to the family economy and also making ethnic minority women more and more active.

However, the survey results show that gender stereotypes still reign in the thinking and activities of people here when participating in production work. Depending on the family, production activities can be mainly handled by the husband, wife or children, but usually the productive labor in these families is assigned according to "man's work", "woman's work".

It can be seen that men often take on tasks that are considered "strong", important and "heavy", need to be more "calculated", "technical" in agriculture, with 3 main tasks in charge of men much higher than the wife: plowing – 60.8%, deep spraying – 64.7%, as a barn for cattle – 61.8%. Meanwhile, women take on the main roles of the "weaker sex", with "light" and "nameless work". The survey results showed that women were mainly responsible for care and gardening (51.9%), and had higher responsibilities than men in planting jobs (wife - 31.2%, husband - 14.6%), harvesting (wife - 37.5%, husband - 14%), product preservation (wife - 24.5%, husband - 6.8%), caring for livestock and poultry (wife - 31.5%, husband – 11.8%).

In summary, there is no denying that many jobs performed by men require more muscle strength, but in fact, the jobs that women undertake, which are considered "light" tasks, take a lot of time, effort and have to be done continuously every day such as: care, gardening, weaving, foraging. The contributions of women in production prove that their abilities are not inferior to men's. However, there is still inequality in the division of productive labor, women have to work too much in agriculture - a hard, time-consuming but technically not very improved field and low income, there are areas of agricultural production where husbands do not share work with wives, leading to a woman having less time to rest and enjoy.

4.1.2. Survey results on access to production resources

Access to resources (land, capital and extension training) between men and women is very different. The percentage of husbands (84.7%) is 10.5 times that of wives (8.1%). Only a handful of women (in the interview issue), knew that existing laws required these properties to be owned by both husband and wife, and that some households had made land red books, had both husband and wife's names as prescribed by law.

"I take it for granted that men own real estate. Men are the head of the family, women just need to take care of everything and build a warm enough roof." (Hmong women in Dien Bien).

The lack of property ownership is the main reason for women's reduced access to capital. Although the trend of both men and women borrowing capital in ethnic minority families is quite high (about 32%), men's chances of accessing capital are still almost twice as high as women's.

"My husband has always been the one to take care of borrowing capital in the family, mostly because the acceptance of men is always higher." – (Nung wife in Son La).

"Borrowing often requires collateral, especially land or real estate, while women are less represented in land use certificates, nor do they play the role of head of household, so it is difficult to get a loan." (officer of Quy Hoa commune, Hoa Binh province).

Access to extension services also varies widely. *"Although women make up the majority of the workforce in the livestock sector, only 1/5 of livestock extension training courses have women participating."* - (Lao Cai provincial officials), *"Similarly, although the majority of rural women participate in farming, they make up only 1/10 of those trained in farming."* The situation of the husband going to school to acquire knowledge of science and technology while the wife is in charge of practice is common in households (of women participating in interviews).

"We women have little opportunity to participate in training sessions because the work is piled up every day, no one can replace it. My husband is the one who will attend these sessions, if anything useful will pass it on to me." (Thai people, Hoa Binh).

"I couldn't go because I had to take care of my family." (Muong people, Son La).

"Men are better able to learn, learn better and apply to work better than women. Women coming home from school can't do it either." (Dao woman, Lao Cai).

It can be seen that ethnic minorities in the Northwest mountains still carry many "gender stereotypes" about the role and capacity of women in land ownership, access to capital and the ability to acquire scientific knowledge. As a result, the percentage of women participating in these activities is very low. Especially in the acquisition of scientific and technical knowledge, the big barrier for women is that "women's knowledge and education level is more limited than men's, even many women are illiterate and do not know Kinh, so the ability to receive knowledge is very difficult while most ethnic minority men can speak and write fluently in the language. universal." In particular, the mentality of timidity, inferiority, and peace of mind, seems to be deeply ingrained in the habits and behaviors of women, which should influence the decision of who will have access to funds for production activities.

4.1.3. Decision-making rights in production activities

In the life of families today, the wife has really become a very important person in building the economic life of the family. They also generate income no less than men, even in many areas of production they are the main source of income. It is from this fact that the economic position of women in families is increasingly enhanced, which is evident in the decision-making power over production and business. Survey data shows that the decision-making power over production and business in the family is now reserved not only for the husband but also for the wife. 135 women (39%) agreed that making decisions at work was discussed and discussed first by both spouses.

However, in reality women are not the main decision-makers in changing the structure of crop livestock, the division of labor, the purchase of supplies, tools of production, trading and sale of products, in some respects their role is limited to the performer, submit to her husband's decisions. Similarly, although the number of people who agreed that both wives made the decision was the largest (142 to 41 percent), the percentage of husbands who made decisions (39 percent) was still higher than women (20 percent).

In summary, in the production activities of ethnic minority families in the Northwest mountains, the role of women is extremely great, they participate in almost all jobs, take on many types of work, status, role of women in access, control of the family's productive resources is raised. However, traditional, gender stereotypes still dominate the division of labor, access to productive resources and decision-making. Women's access, control and decision-making in production are limited and remain unequal compared to men.

4.2. Gender equality in reproduction activities

4.2.1. Division of labor

Reproduction is an activity that takes up a lot of time, both indirectly and directly creates economic efficiency for each household, carrying out this work not only as a measure of the position and importance of the husband or wife, but also as a basis for assessing the role of each gender in relation to the family economy. In the concept of ethnic minorities (interviewed), they often consider this as an obvious job, which the woman must take on, as "errand" work, with no value, so without pay, not considered income-generating work.

Table 4. The role of women in reproduction

Performer Type of work	Wife	Husband	Both	Different
	%	%	%	%
Cook	68,7%	8,9%	15,8%	6,6%
Laundry	71,3%	4,1%	19,3%	5,3%
Go to the market	68,5%	7,8%	11,3%	12,4%
Hold money	58,6%	29,0%	11,8%	0,6%
Caring for and teaching your child	38,2%	5,6%	45,7%	10,5%
Care for the elderly	19,5%	12,3%	59,7%	8,5%
Water intake	74,1%	8,6%	12,5%	4,8%
Pounding rice	41,8%	13,0%	42,1%	3,1%

Source: archaeological research

Currently, in ethnic minority families in the Northwest region, there has been the participation and sharing of men in reproduction activities. In things such as: caring for and teaching children, taking care of the elderly and sick, if comparing the proportion of main workers, the wife accounts for a higher proportion than the husband, but these are not necessarily the jobs only the wife performs, the combination of husband and wife is the highest index is 59.7% (elderly care), 45.7% (childcare and teaching), 42.1% (pounding rice). The sharing of these jobs between husband and wife shows that families greatly appreciate the importance of these jobs, which is a positive change in the division of labor in reproduction.

Despite changes towards equality in reproduction labor, women are still the main undertakers, the intensity of women's labor in this field is very large and many times higher than that of men. For example, the percentage of women who undertake water intake is 9 times that of men. In all the work of reproduction, the woman always assumes a greater role than the man.

"These are jobs for wives. That's the general norm and previous generations have done the same." (Nung women, Lao Cai).

"These tasks are light but repetitive, day in and day out keeping me busy from morning to night. But a wife who can't handle these jobs is a shame, a lazy wife who doesn't know how to take care of her family." (Thai women, Hoa Binh).

"Unlike women, men are supposed to do heavier, more important jobs. Miscellaneous errands are women's." (Dao women, Dien Bien).

From the analysis data and interview answers, it is possible to comment that the prejudice in the gender-based division of labor for ethnic minority women still exists quite heavily. Women in ethnic minority families have to take on the majority of reproduction work, which in fact makes a great contribution to the family economy, not only providing inputs to human development, but also generating tremendous spiritual energy for their lives.

But women's own appreciation of this work is not enough, most of them think that it is light work, mainly in the family, not hard work and these jobs, women do better because women themselves are skillful and neat. If there is a sense of struggle, the woman follows the framework of traditional practices, in order to achieve harmony in the family. In the absence of work sharing, they still tend to avoid breaking the ideal pattern of community, which they themselves have been immersed in since childhood. From a human rights and gender perspective, the practice of traditional customs, which can sometimes disadvantage women, cannot be seen as a justification for unfair treatment of women.

4.2.2. Access to resources in reproduction

The survey results showed that women were participating in and contributing to the increasing family income because *"if the role of making money is only that of men, then it is difficult to ensure the support of the family"*. But the notion of women being pure money keepers hasn't changed much.

"In the family, the man is the basket, making money to feed the family, and the woman is the ark that preserves and keeps the capital." (Tay woman, Lao Cai)

The results in the survey (table 4) show that in the family, the majority of money managers are women, but if it is considered that women's income in the family is a manifestation of equality, it is completely incorrect. Because *"even though they are keepers of money, women are not actively spent."*

In terms of family planning, women are still considered primarily responsible for ensuring reproductive health and the use of contraceptives. The percentage of men who actively use contraceptive methods accounts for only 14.5%. The interview results showed that family planning methods used by ethnic minority families in the Northwest mountains such as intrauterine devices, oral contraceptives, birth control injections, and abortions are still mainly focused on women. This discrepancy comes in part from the inadequate knowledge of reproductive health of ethnic minority men, with many arguing that the use of contraceptives such as sterilization will make *"men stupid."* Or because men do not know how to use contraceptive tools correctly, they refuse to take these measures and leave contraception to their wives. On the other hand, many ethnic minority women themselves believe that *"carrying out family planning is the responsibility of the wife."*

The conception of the role of women as dependent on their husbands in patriarchal societies continues to influence the health and reproductive behavior of ethnic minority women in the Northwest Mountains. The fact that reproductive health protection programs are still aimed at women, perhaps creates an additional burden on women who are already very busy with other responsibilities in the family.

4.2.3. Right to make decisions in reproduction activities

The survey results of the study showed that both spouses' spending decisions accounted for the highest proportion of activities such as: *"shopping for furniture", "building a house", "children's education"*. Despite having decision-making power over spending important household chores and having financial means in hand, the fact that money holders, money managers in ethnic minority families in the Northwest Mountains, do not mean that they have the right to decide to use money according to their subjective will.

The majority of women in ethnic minority families in the Northwest mountains are just money holders, entitled to spend on *"sundry items"* of daily life such as going to the market to buy items and items with little money, even the decision of women to go to the market to buy items with little money of their wives is 5 times higher than that of their husbands. As for large expenditures, which have a significant impact on the economic life of families, the decisive role of the man is the main one.

"I only take care of my daily shopping expenses, and spending a large amount of money or on important decisions, in particular, will be decided by my husband." (Tay women, Son La).

"The purchase of expensive items or the construction of houses will be decided by my husband" (Muong woman, Son La).

In terms of deciding the number of children, both spouses have a voice in the family (85% of ethnic women involved agree with this result). However, the final decider is the husband. Although the wife is the bearer of pain, she is not the main decision maker about having children, so the proportion of families with large children is a challenge for ethnic minority families in the Northwest mountains today in the struggle to eliminate poverty.

"It requires a lot of health and as many people do as possible. The more labor a family has, the more food it collects. That's why my husband decided he needed more children." – (Dao woman, Lao Cai).

The role of the gender of children in ethnic minority families surveyed also has a large gap. Many women find that girls need to be seen more fairly with boys. Many mothers (about 30%) said they prefer to raise their daughters and would prefer to have their first child, a girl. However, these women are still under a lot of pressure to have sons from the husband's family. Most women claim that their lineage expects a lot from the number of sons in the family.

"The concept of my family is that the more sons a family has, the more power and voice there is in the clan. Therefore, we and our husband have to work hard to give birth to a son." (Hmong women, Dien Bien).

"Here the notion is that boys are the breadwinners of the family, girls are just homemakers. Therefore, when giving birth, if a son is born, the placenta will be buried under the main pillar with the meaning that the son is the pillar. If you give birth to a girl, the placenta is buried under the bed with the idea that the girl is the one who takes care of the housework." (Officer of Hoa Binh Province).

Many families and women themselves believe that boys are the pride of the family, "the *one who takes care of the smoke later, raises and takes care of their parents in old age, daughters only help the house once, sons help the house all their lives.*" The customary laws of some peoples stipulate that only sons can inherit property, houses and land, and this customary law remains strong in the lives of people in the villages. If there is no son, the woman must agree to let her husband look for someone else to have a son, or she must go looking for another son to be able to adopt.

In summary, although relations in ethnic minority families in the northwest mountains of Vietnam tend to be more egalitarian and democratic, men, the breadwinners of the family, still have more advantages than women, a more weighty voice than women in big family decisions. Gender equality in domestic work does not mean equally dividing household chores between men and women, nor is it forcing women to give up taking care of the family. But the burden of dual roles falls on the shoulders of ethnic minority women, which hinders their development when they want to improve their development capacity and participate in the labor market to enhance their status.

4.3. Gender equality in community activities

The survey results show that community work is not only the work of men, but women are more involved and have more say in participating in community work. Specifically, in jobs such as vegetarianism, ancestral marriage, visiting relatives, and village cleaning, the participation rate of men versus women was not significantly different, and respondents said that both husband and wife had the same level of participation in community work.

Table 5. The role of women in community activism

Performer Type of work	Wife	Husband	Both	Different
	%	%	%	%
Attendance/hospitality	25,0%	37,0%	35,4%	2,6%
Village meeting	17,8%	51,0%	28,0%	3,2%
Communication with the authorities	24,0%	39,0%	33,0%	4,0%
Commemoration of the village	5,6%	61,2%	32,0%	1,2%
Reception	24,0%	34,0%	38,0%	4,0%
Cleaning villages and hamlets	31,5%	24,8%	29,0%	14,7%

Source: archaeological research

In participating in community activities, the lowest index of women was participation in village commemorations (5.6%). Women are less involved in village commemoration activities, because according to the customary laws of ethnic minorities, men are always responsible for performing religious belief ceremonies within the framework of families and villages. Men are also the ones who perform foreign affairs functions, attending the affairs of the family on behalf of the family and villages. The only indicator that women are more involved than men is participating in cleaning and cleaning villages.

"Men are not only labor-intensive tasks, but also include responsibilities related to external social interaction."
– (Nung women, Dien Bien).

"Men play a decisive role in the administration, internal and external affairs of the family. Even many villages here keep customs that prevent women from participating in community activities such as funerals, weddings, meetings." (officer of Muong Lay commune in Dien Bien province).

In terms of decisions to participate in community activities, although women take the lead (24%), or both spouses participate equally (33.5%) accounting for a good proportion, men are still the main ones, the proportion of men participating in regular meetings is higher than women. It is worth noting that when going to meetings, the majority of women from ethnic minority groups in the Northwest mountains rarely participate in speeches, because they feel "lack of knowledge, little understanding of meeting contents", they are "self-conscious and afraid to speak in public". Moreover, due to social prejudice, in village meetings run mostly by men, many of whom are not aware that encouraging women to speak is not always supported by men. There are women who speak so enthusiastically that some (both men and women) are considered masculine and look at them unsympathetically, this treatment has reduced the enthusiasm of the sisters and affected the quality of their contributions.

In summary, like production, reproduction, in community activities, men often take on the main roles in jobs that are considered more important, even many times higher than women, women only play a secondary role.

4.4. Aspirations for gender equality of ethnic minority women in the Northwest

The survey results on changing roles and current positions in domestic work showed that the opinions of subjects (ethnic minority women in the Northwest mountains) divided into 2 streams. One view is that issues such as the division of labor, decision-making and ideology of men and women in their families, clans and communities need to be changed in a way that recognizes women's roles, contributions and capacities more equitably. On the other hand, a section of women think that current problems do not need to change because it is a way of life that they have maintained for generations.

Specifically, about 61.5% of women said that it is necessary to improve the status of wives and women in the family. These people argue that ethnic minority women are under a lot of pressure from work and, at the urging of their families and communities, to participate more in field work. They argue that the field work they are shouldering needs to be shared further.

"How can a woman take on all the farm chores and housework. I had to wake up at 4 a.m. and be tired all day in the field, coming home by the time the sun had set. I don't have time to take care of myself, be close to my kids, go get together with my friends." - (Hmong women in Lao Cai).

"In order to continue my current business, I need a lot of time to learn and trade outside. Therefore, I asked my husband to share more housework. And in fact, my husband is the one who takes care of the main business at home." (Thai women in Son La.)

In terms of labor equality, mostly field jobs and heavy labor, many women argue that they cannot take on the same amount of work as men due to health problems and because they need more time for housework and childcare.

"How can I do the same amount of work as my husband, this will take up all my time. My child will live as an orphan. This only leads to poverty and suffering" – (Phu Lá ethnic women, Dien Bien).

"How can I work as a man? I'm a mom. I gave birth. I'm pregnant. I can't work as a man because of this." (Hmong women in Son La).

This can be seen as a contradiction in the issue of gender equality and also a difficult point in making decisions and policies in improving equality for women in labor. How is it considered equal? Does the amount of work, time and effort required to be balanced (in physical terms) to be considered equal? That is the problem for policy makers to implement gender equality.

On the other hand, some women do not approve of changing the status of work assignments as well as issues of decision-making and the current role of women. Although they are aware that tasks that are considered "light" actually take a lot of time, effort and have to be done continuously every day. It is worth noting that, although most of them believe that women can do jobs such as cutting down big trees or driving plows and vice versa men can do jobs such as weeding and fertilizing, they say they should not change, because it will "lose their masculine or feminine traits and, most importantly, fear of others." *laughing.* They added, *"such a division of labor has been around for a long time, and has become the norm that does not need to be changed."* This shows that gender stereotypes about domestic labor exist not only in the perceptions of men, but also in women themselves – those who have been taught and nurtured according to the motif of mothers and grandmothers before and in turn will also "contribute" to the upbringing of daughters as such. It is in that spirit that a woman's life is like a closed circle, from an early age they have to sacrifice for the economy and family welfare, until they grow up to become wives and mothers, they continue to mistakenly sacrifice their rights for their husbands and children and their families.

In summary, gender relations in northwest mountainous ethnic minority communities have been more open about the roles and status of spouses. According to the survey women themselves, their lives have changed a lot, many women no longer think that only "housework" is their job. However, in ethnic minority families in the Northwest mountains today, there are still basically many gender stereotypes, the division of labor still follows the traditional view of "manhood", "womanhood". This assignment comes from the notion that men are "strong men" who must take on "heavy tasks", need "calculation" and "technique", while women of the "weaker sex" should be in charge of "light tasks", "unnamed jobs". The distinction between "men" and "women" has in fact reduced the value of women's labor, which has hindered them from accessing and controlling resources for

development, limiting decision-making power in family labor. In the family the wife is still dependent on the husband, the man. While performing more housework and livestock and farming tasks than the husband, the wife has a much less decisive say on important issues than the husband. It should be noted that inequalities in access to and enjoyment of family resources still have a large gap between men and women, between husband and wife. In fact, the implementation of inequality in family labor of ethnic minorities in the Northwest mountains still faces many difficulties and challenges.

5. Conclusions

5.1. *Discuss research results*

The research results show that, in the context of limited socio-economic conditions in the northwest ethnic minority region of Vietnam, production productivity is not high, women play an important role in production labor. They show responsibility in ensuring the quality of life and earning economic benefits for the family. There is no large disparity in participation in production work from a gender perspective. From an ideological perspective, however, there are still notions of "manhood" and "womanhood." Research has also shown that women are largely responsible for jobs that require more diligence and time. Despite this, the man who is said to work harder less shares the work with his wife. Therefore, the intensity of the woman's productive labor is quite high, with little time for rest and enjoyment. Along with that, the percentage of ethnic minority women accessing land ownership, loans and extension services is very low.

As for the reproduction operation, it is largely done by the woman. Much influenced by the old ideology, the ethnic minority woman is in charge of most household chores such as cooking, doing laundry, going to the market, taking care of children and dummies. At the same time, women also played a major role in the use of reproductive health protections (84.5%). This implies the perception of ethnic minorities that men only do big things, not small things in the family.

Previously, only men participated in community activities, including ghost activities, weddings, village meetings, communication with the authorities, etc. However, in recent years, women have become more involved and have a greater voice in community activism. This number is not large, though. This is explained by the fact that the majority of household heads are men. Therefore, they take the right to represent and decide in the family.

5.2. *Contradictions in the implementation of gender equality for ethnic minority women in the northwest mountains of Vietnam*

First, the challenge between the economic premise requirement to realize gender equality in family labor and the poor and backward economic situation in the Northwest Mountains. However, the economic conditions of ethnic minority families are very difficult, incomes are low. This makes them not even qualified to take care of meals and clothes for their families. As a result, expenses and investments have to be cut, and even ethnic minority women rarely have the opportunity to enjoy life. At the same time, poverty is also the cause of inequality in the division of labor. Living in the hills and mountains of northwest Vietnam, ethnic women have little access to advanced and modern labor tools such as machines. In the process of production labor, tools are mainly pre-industrial rudimentary materials such as pickaxes, plows, meals. The level of hard work combined with the intensity of labor makes a woman have little time to rest. At the same time, miss the opportunity to study, access technology - information and enjoy culture.

Secondly, the conflict between the need to raise people's knowledge and awareness and the situation of low people's intelligence, the awareness of gender equality is not high in the ethnic minority delta. Improving education is the most solid path in socio-economic development. However, the level of education in ethnic minority areas in northwest Vietnam is still very low. Therefore, women are not clearly aware of the gender equality perspective. At the same time, backward views ingrained in the subconscious make them lead doomed

lifestyles. Not only that, the lower level of education and technology compared to men is a barrier that makes it more difficult for them to find a job, low income and the nature of the job is more difficult. Research shows that nearly 80% of ethnic minority women in the Northwest Mountains are self-employed or unpaid domestic workers. Most importantly, women with low education are at a disadvantage in raising and forming ideas for their children. The consequence is the issue of raising people's knowledge for children – future generations in ethnic minority areas.

Third, it contradicts the long-standing existence of many backward customs. Longstanding social notions conveyed male-dominated thoughts of contempt for women. This ideology has been deeply ingrained in the subconscious of ethnic people. They claim that women were born to work as family care workers and productive laborers. Because of that, ethnic minority women have a doomed lifestyle, without the spirit of rising. Long-standing practices such as child marriage, opium smoking, and alcoholism are passed down from generation to generation. The husband and children become a burden for the family due to insufficient working health. From there, the family economy became exhausted, the burden of labor was once again shifted to the woman. In addition, a part of the people is inclusive, does not pay attention to economic development, on the contrary, only worries about eating and spending, causing the family economy to go down more and more. It is these reasons that make it more difficult to abolish backward customs.

Fourth, the contradiction between the trend of women's liberation and the psychological well-being of ethnic minority women. According to Mac doctrine and Ho Chi Minh's thought, women's liberation is an inevitable trend. The level of women's liberation is a measure of the level of development of society (S.Phurie). However, the liberation of ethnic minority women is facing many difficulties. Objective reasons are mentioned such as geographical location, socio-economic conditions, people's intellectual level ... However, the root cause is that ethnic minority women are not aware of their position and role in the family and in society. They are always doomed, and lack the spirit to rise in all areas. They somehow accepted and served their husbands unconditionally. This ideology is deeply influenced by social prejudices and backward views. At the same time, they do not have much access to the rights to protect women as prescribed by law. This means that overwork, women's enjoyment is considered secondary, not even taken into account, which is considered a violence against labor in which the victims are mainly women. Self-deprecation often causes women to not fully develop their abilities to serve the development of their families and communities. Moreover, self-deprecation makes a woman's self-worth unrecognized in the family and in society.

5.3. Solution

Firstly, raising education and awareness of gender equality for ethnic minorities. Increase the mobilization of ethnic minority children to school, ensuring that women and ethnic minority children can read and write. Continue to promote education and counseling, career orientation for ethnic minority children and women. This can be done in schools, villages or households. Strengthen courses on extension of agriculture – forestry – fishery for middle-aged ethnic minority women who cannot speak, read and write in mandarin. These courses need to be tailored to the needs, promote practical training to achieve high efficiency. At the same time, training to improve the representative capacity of ethnic minority women.

Second, encourage ethnic minority women to participate in economic mastery. Increase support for ethnic minority women to access resources of the National Target Program on Socio-Economic Development of Ethnic Minorities and Mountainous Areas for the period 2021-2030. Accordingly, integrating gender equality issues in projects on agricultural and forestry production development. Specifically, maximizing the access to information of ethnic minorities. Specify the gender ratio of participants and beneficiaries of these projects. The initial orientation figure can be at least 30% / gender for the period 2022 - 2025 and at least 40% / gender for the next period. At the same time, the study proposes to allocate at least 30% of the project 3 budget to projects implemented by ethnic minority women. The basic level of access can help ethnic minority women get

acquainted with economic and social development activities. From there, there is enough awareness and confidence to carry out further projects.

Third, encourage ethnic minority women to participate in local representative organizations. On that basis, helping them to approach and participate in the inevitable trend – women's liberation. Here, women can participate in the process of building, administering and managing relevant issues in the community. This implies supporting ethnic minority women to be bold, dare to learn to dare and adapt to gender equality rights in society. Specifically, on the basis of the gender equality situation in each locality, a plan on the number of ethnic minority women participating in the representative and management apparatus in the community is proposed. The initial management may be limited to a small range that fits their capacity. Promote the pilot construction of ethnic women to participate in the construction and operation of the management system. From there, evaluate the effectiveness, detect new problems and come up with appropriate solutions. Experience from pilot models is the basis for building a reasonable practical model and replicating the model. Accordingly, gender mainstreaming is applied in the implementation of the plan to develop ethnic minority cadres, civil servants and officials in the new era. Promote gender equality in the work of creating sources, recruiting and fostering associated with the placement, use and promotion of ethnic minority female cadres under the Project "Supporting gender equality activities in ethnic minority areas in the period of 2018 - 2025". Organizing training courses, fostering the capacity of female staff with support for expenses such as the cost of sending children or arranging a babysitting place, travel expenses, etc.

Fourth, strengthen communication activities to change gender stereotypes and stereotypes against ethnic minority women in particular and ethnic minorities in general. Universalize regulations and legal documents on women's rights, regulations on domestic violence prevention and control. Integrating knowledge that changes old perspectives through school and practical activities.

Fifth, promote the development of infrastructure in ethnic minority areas. Budget investment for basic infrastructure such as transport, electricity, schools, healthcare, markets, etc. These are essential infrastructure requirements for the development and access to modern technology of ethnic minority people. At the same time, it is also a method of attracting domestic and foreign investment to develop the economy in this region. Regarding gender equality in promoting infrastructure development, in particular, stipulate the proportion of ethnic minority women who can participate and have a representative voice in decisions related to local infrastructure development. Promote capacity building to participate in decisions on infrastructure development.

In addition, research and develop effective support service delivery models in ethnic minority areas in terms of care for the elderly, young children and the sick; clean water services to ethnic minority population clusters to free up the labor of ethnic minority households for unpaid care work.

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